

Derivation of Aquatic Life Criteria for Heavy Metals and Their Ecological Risk Assessment in Ntawogba Creek, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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Abstract

Heavy metal attracts considerable attention globally due to their elevated levels in water bodies, persistent characteristic and toxicity to aquatic organisms. Aquatic Life Criteria (ALC) for heavy metals are vital for precise ecological risk assessment and have not often been derived before for water bodies in Nigeria. Given this concern, the aim of the present study is to optimize the ALCs of five targeted Heavy Metals and to evaluate their ecological risks in Ntawogba Creek. The toxicological information for cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), chromium (VI), arsenic (III) and zinc (Zn) were collected from different databases, screened, and used to develop ALC for these heavy metals. US EPA recommended method for deriving aquatic life criteria was employed to derive the short-term (Criterion Maximum Concentration) and long-term (Criterion Continuous Concentration) of five heavy, then hazard quotient method (HQ) was applied for ecological risk assessment for 5 heavy metals by dividing the heavy metals concentration in surface water by the derived long-term aquatic life criteria. The developed aquatic life criteria revealed that the criterion maximum concentrations (CMC) and criterion continuous concentration (CCC) for Pb, Cr(VI), Cd, As(III), and Zn were 8.5, 48.5, 1.43, 169.2, 104.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 1.68, 9.79, 0.29, 34, 21.09 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. The ecological risks were 0.39, 0.28, 6.33, 1.57, and 1.47 mg/L for Pb, Cr, Cd, As, and Zn, respectively. Cd, As, and Zn were found to be of concern; the HQ exhibited unacceptable risk (HQ >1), while Pb and Cr indicated no significant risk (HQ <1) in the aquatic ecosystem. These results indicated that aquatic life criteria should be adopted in determining the ecological risk associated with heavy metals in surface water. This study will serve as a reference for establishing aquatic life criteria and determining ecological risk for protecting aquatic life in Nigeria.

Keywords: Aquatic life criteria, Criterion maximum concentration, Criterion continuous concentration, Hazard Quotient

Introduction

Heavy metal pollution has been proven to have severe effects on both the ecosystem, and aquatic organism as a result of their

capacity to penetrate the food chain, their biological toxicity, persistence, and lack of degradability (Shuhaimi-Othman *et al.*, 2013; Hong *et al.*, 2020). They are

naturally occurring beneath the earth, and many of them ascend into the surface biotas due to anthropogenic activities such as mineral extraction, metal processing, agrochemicals, application of pesticides, untreated domestic and industrial wastewater discharge (Rehman *et al.*, 2018, Rosado *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, they can be redistributed during storms or by other benthic processes such as bioturbation (Kelderman & Osman, 2007, Knox *et al.*, 2020, Kumar *et al.*, 2022). Heavy metals, unlike organic pollutants, are not formed or destroyed biologically, and since metals that are toxic cannot be easily removed from the aquatic environment via natural courses except from washout or burial, their concentration levels are frequently raised, posing risk to the ecosystem and aquatic organism. In this context, heavy metals (HMs) bioaccumulate in aquatic organism (Rahman *et al.*, 2012; Heshmati *et al.*, 2017; Ali and Khan, 2019) bio-magnify in the food web, result in greater ecological risk (Zhang *et al.*, 2012; Ali and Khan, 2019; Fang *et al.*, 2019) and endangering neighboring human community (Mishra *et al.*, 2019; Lawal *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, to some degree, aquatic species have the ability to concentrate and accumulate heavy metals. However, heavy metals will have major deleterious impacts on associated indicators and even life activities when their concentration and toxicity levels beyond aquatic creatures' tolerance. These effects include changes in species diversity and survival rates may arise simultaneously from genetic

mutations or variations (Hong *et al.*, 2020), lipid peroxidation (Morcillo *et al.*, 2016), inhibition of enzyme activities (Zhen *et al.*, 2017) and in severe situation results in mortality of aquatic organism. Therefore, it is imperative to protect the aquatic ecosystem and organism from the adverse effect of HMs.

One essential tool for protecting aquatic biotas from emerging pollution is the Aquatic Life Criteria (ALC) (Zheng *et al.*, 2017). According to Wu *et al.*, (2012), ALC is the maximum permissible levels of toxic substances in water that, under certain natural circumstances, will not pose short or long term negatively impact on selected protected aquatic life. The aquatic life criteria serve as the cornerstone for the protection of water quality and give environmental protection organizations a solid scientific foundation for preserving aquatic ecosystems. Additionally, Wu *et al.*, (2008) stated that aquatic life criteria are currently the fundamental theoretical and indispensable scientific basis that environmental protection agencies need to develop water quality standards, assess water quality, and carry out efficient water quality control procedures. Numerous countries, such as the US, Australia, China, and Canada, have set up their own ALC, using either single or double threshold value systems. For aquatic organisms, criteria maximum concentrations (CMCs) and criteria continuous concentrations (CCCs) are frequently used as thresholds for identifying acute and chronic harm, respectively.

Nevertheless, nations like Nigeria are yet to develop their aquatic life criteria for protection of aquatic organisms. Due to lack of ALC, the conventional water quality standards (WQSs) for heavy metals in Nigeria are primarily centered on international criteria or values that have different climatic conditions than those of Nigeria. As a result, there is an absence of a scientific basis in Nigeria for risk assessment and environmental management of water ecosystems. Therefore, it is imperative that a baseline study on aquatic life criteria be conducted in compliance with Nigerian national conditions in order to manage the country's water environment. Consequently, ALC for priority or emergent contaminants in Nigeria must be developed based, at least in part, on how the country's aquatic biota reacts to those chemicals.

In regard of the aforementioned significant challenges, the purpose of this work is to develop an ALC for heavy metals. In order to achieve this, aquatic species with acute toxicity were selected based on the heavy metal toxicity data *set already* available in the Ecotox database. Using data analysis as a basis, a ALC for heavy metals was developed in accordance with US EPA guidelines. Furthermore, the developed aquatic life criteria were used to determine the ecological risk associated with heavy metal in the study area.

Materials and Methods

The study area Ntawogba, is situated on the western border of the city of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The water

course can be found flanked at latitudes of 4° 47' and 4° 49' N and longitudes of 6° 59' and 7° 00' E. The area has a climate likened to that of the tropical equatorial latitude, with an average precipitation of 2719mm and a temperature that fluctuates between 22° C and 32° C all through the year (Gobo, 1998; Gobo *et al.*, 2008). The Ntawogba Creek is a stream that originates in the northern area (Orazi Forest) and flows southward into the Bonny Sea, with a water zone of just about 8.07km. The river is a major water resource used for drinking, commercial and industrial activities in Port Harcourt metropolis. The water body receives an estimate of 4500 L/day of waste comprising of petroleum product, specifically from crankshaft oil, more than 250,000 L/day from home waste, about 158kg/day from human waste, metals, and solid waste such as paper and polyethylene bags. The area is characterized by constant rainfalls that occur almost every day from the month of May-November and a dry season from December-April (Gobo 1998; Gobo *et al.*, 2008). Overtime, these activities have deteriorated the water quality of the creek. Twenty (20) surface water samples were obtained from Ntawogba creek. 1 litre of water samples were collected from the surface of each sample station and placed in sterile polypropylene containers. The water samples were well-preserved using 1% Nitric acid (HNO₃) and placed in an ice chest at 4°C till it was conveyed to the lab for further analysis (APHA, 2012; Pandiyan *et al.* 2021).

Figure 1
Map showing sampling stations of water in Ntawogba Creek

Sample Analysis and Quality Control

In analyzing the water sample, 100ml of water sample was measured into a 250ml beaker; about 10ml of sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), 10ml of nitric acid (HNO_3) and 5ml of perchloric acid ($HClO_4$) were added in a ratio of 2:2:1 respectively. The mixture was heated in a water bath for about 2 hours at $105^\circ C$ till it reduced to 20 ml. It was allowed to cool for 10-20mins; the sample was filtered using a filter paper into a 100ml volumetric flask. The sample was falsified with distilled water to 100ml; put the sample into a 120ml white plastic container. The atomic absorption spectrophotometer Raleigh WFF 320 model was used to determine the concentration of Cd, Cr, Pb, As, and Zn in the samples. During the analysis of

samples, procedural blanks, sample duplicate entries, and recovery rate testing were conducted for quality control and quality assurance (QA/ QC). The comparative nonconformity of the replica samples was 5%, and the recovery rate for the five (5) heavy metals ranged from 86.3 percent to 107.8 percent.

Collection of Toxicity Data for ALC Prediction

In agreement with the US EPA guidelines for ALC (US EPA, 1985), data on at least 28 non-native species were obtained. The toxicity data, for five heavy metals: cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), chromium (Cr), arsenic (As), and Zinc (Zn) were gained from the Ecotox database (<https://cfpub.epa.gov/ecotox>) and published literature. They were drawn

from different taxonomic groups including insecta (*Chironomus Javanus*, *Chironomus Plumosus*, *Culicoids Furens*, *Chironomus Tetans*, *Chironomus Kiiensis*), amphibian (*Rana Huanrenensis*), fish (*Salmo Gairdneri*, *Poecilia Reticulata*, *Cyprinus Carpio*, *Rhodeus Ocellatus*, *Misgurnus Anguillicaudatus*, *Oncorhynchus Mykiss*, *Pimephelas Promelas*, *Lepomis Gibbosus*, *Colisa Fasciatus*, *Carassius Auratus*), annelid (*Nais Elinguis*, *Tubifex Tubifex*), rotifera (*Brachionus calyciflorus*), crustaceans (*Macrobrachium Lanchestri*, *Gammarus Pseudolimnaeus*, *Daphnia Magna*, *Macrobrachium Lamarrei*), mollusca (*Limnoperna Fortunei*, *Physa Heterostrophea*, *Melanoides Tuberculata*, *Margarga Melanoides*), Plant (*Lemna Minor*). These organisms were also used in previous research to derive ALC for chromium, lead, cadmium, arsenic, zinc aquatic life criteria (Wu *et al.*, 2012, Lee *et al.*, 2020; Li *et al.*, 2021).

Data Analysis

Aquatic Life Criteria Derivation

According to the available data and the 96-h-LC₅₀ values, the acute toxicity data was examined. The ALC for the heavy metals was calculated using the US EPA stipulated guidelines for deriving aquatic life criteria (US EPA, 1985).

The following formulas were employed to calculate the criterion maximum concentration (CMC).

$$S^2 = \frac{\Sigma[(\ln GMAV)^2] - [\Sigma(\ln GMAV)]^2/4}{\Sigma P - (\Sigma\sqrt{P})^2/4} \quad (eqn. 1)$$

$$P = \frac{r}{n + 1} \quad (eqn. 2)$$

$$L = \frac{\Sigma(\ln GMAV) - S(\Sigma\sqrt{P})}{4} \quad (eqn. 3)$$

$$A = S\sqrt{0.05 + L} \quad (eqn. 4)$$

$$FAV = e^A \quad (eqn. 5)$$

$$CMC = \frac{FAV}{2} \quad (eqn. 6)$$

Where:

GMAV= Genus means acute value

P = cumulative probability

FAV = final acute value

The GMAVs were arranged in an ascending order, with r ranging from 1 to n, indicating the designated sequence for each GMAV. The FAV was computed by means of four GMAV values with P values close to 0.05. The final acute value (FAV) was calculated in this research using the FAV formula from the guidelines. The FAV was divided by two to derive the criteria for maximum concentration (CMC). The FAV was divided by the acute chronic ratio (ACR) to derive the final chronic value (FCV). ACRs was utilized in measuring chronic toxicity for metals and aquatic organism with known acute toxicity but little or no knowledge of chronic toxicity. Due to deficiency in chronic data for the species adopted in the acute toxicity of this study, a total average value of 9.9 for the ACR was employed based on a finding by May *et al.*, (2016) who deduced an ACR average value focusing on same-species (invertebrate and fish) pairs of acute and maximum agreeable toxicant concentration levels for pesticides, metals, and other organic elements.

Ecological Risk Assessment

The probable effects of heavy metal toxicity on the organisms in the research region were assessed using an ecological risk assessment. The Hazard Quotient (HQ) procedure was used to determine ecological risk by dividing the heavy metal concentration in water by the pertinent long-term aquatic life criteria (CCC) values and is frequently employed in ecological risk assessments of aquatic environments (Gao *et al.*, 2020, Suter, 2008; Wang *et al.*, 2020,) using equation (eqn. 7).

$$HQ = \frac{EC}{CCC} \quad (eqn. 7)$$

Ecological risk was divided into 2 categories HQ < 1 (No Risk); HQ > 1 (High Risk) (Dong *et al.*, 2020; Li *et al.*, 2019).

Additionally, mean, standard deviation, Box plot, line graph and bar chart were conducted using Ms. Excel 2016.

Results and discussion

Aquatic Life Criteria for of Heavy Metals. In this study, only toxicity data based on 96h-LC₅₀ were gathered and a number of 8 data set each were collected for Pb, Cr (IV), Cd, As (III) and Zn, respectively. The details of collected toxicity data were listed in Table 1. The toxicity data in all for the five heavy metals were from a total of 28 species including fishes, alga invertebrates, and invertebrates. A wide distinction was observed in the values for Pb with values varied from 0.035 - 34.6

mgL⁻¹ and an average value of 9.02 mgL⁻¹. Concentrations for Cr (IV) varied from 0.65 - 67 mgL⁻¹ with a mean value of 38.58 mgL⁻¹. Concentrations for Cd varied from 0.007 - 0.4 mgL⁻¹ with an average value of 0.12 mgL⁻¹. Concentrations for As (III) varied from 0.68 - 38.43 mgL⁻¹ with an average value of 13.41 mgL⁻¹. Concentrations for Zn varied from 0.6 - 20.1 mgL⁻¹ with an average value of 7.91 mgL⁻¹. Owing to the deficiency in the availability of toxicity data based on resident species, non-native species were used for this study. Recent studies showed that there was no statistically significant (p>0.05) variance in criteria between species native to a geographical area and non-native species (Jin *et al.*, 2015; Wang *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2021). The most sensitive species to Cr (IV) and As (III) were insect's, *Chironomus Tetan* individual, whereas *Pimephales Promelas* was most sensitive to Zn. Intriguingly, crustaceans were most sensitive species for Pd and Cd, *Macrobrachium Lanchestri* respectively. The result was in consonance with earlier studies, in which crustaceans exhibited greater sensitivity to Pb and Cd than others (Shuhaimi-Othman *et al.*, 2013, Wu *et al.*, 2012; Zheng *et al.*, 2017; Li *et al.*, 2021).

The acute toxicity data of aquatic species was used to derive the short-term and long-term aquatic life criteria. ALC of five heavy metals were derived using the USEPA guideline for deriving aquatic life criteria (USEPA 1985).

Table 1
Acute Toxicity Data of Pb, Cr (VI), Cd, As(III), and Zn to 28 freshwater species.

Metals	Ranks	Species	96h-LC ₅₀ (mgL ⁻¹)
Lead	1	M. Lanchestri	0.035
	2	C. Furens	0.4
	3	N. Elinguis	0.58
	4	C. Javanus	0.72
	5	R. Ocellatus	6.78
	6	M. Anguillicaudatus	12.77
	7	C. Plumosus	16.2
	8	C. Tetans	34.67
Chromium (VI)	1	C. Tetans	0.65
	2	M. Lamarrei	1.84
	3	B. Calyciflorus	2.61
	4	P. Heterostrophea	40.6
	5	S. Gairdneri	45.0
	6	P. Promelas	59.0
	7	C. Fasciatus	60.0
	8	G. Pseudolimnaeus	67.0
Cadmium	1	M. Lanchestri	0.007
	2	S. Gairdneri	0.01
	3	N. Elinguis	0.027
	4	G. Pseudolimnaeus	0.05
	5	C. Javanus	0.06
	6	P. Reticulata	0.17
	7	L. Minor	0.2
	8	C. Plumosus	0.4
Arsenic (III)	1	C. Tetans	0.680
	2	L. Fortunei	3.08
	3	D. Magna	5.278
	4	T. Tubifix	8.87
	5	C. Kiinesis	9.63
	6	O. Mykiss	15.3
	7	C. Auratus	26.04
	8	R. Huanrenensis	38.43
Zinc	1	P. Promelas	0.6
	2	N. Elinguis	0.91
	3	M. Tuberculata	3.9
	4	C. Javanus	5.57
	5	M. Melanoides	7.495
	6	C. Carpio	7.8
	7	M. Anquillicaudatus	16.91
	8	L. Gibbosus	20.1

The derived aquatic life criteria are demonstrated in Table 2. The CMC and CCC value for Pb was 8.3 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 1.68 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively, the CMC and CCC for lead were below those prescribed by USEPA threshold which was stated to be 65.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 2.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively. The CMC and CCC of Cr(IV), Cd and As(III) were 48.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 1.43 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 1.69 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 9.79 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 0.29 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, 34.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively.

The derived CMC and CCC for Cd were similar to those prescribed by USEPA whereas that of Cr(IV) were three times above USEPA recommended short-term threshold of 16 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ while its CCC were below the prescribed long-term threshold (USEPA, 1985; 2005). However, CMC and CCC of Zn 104.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 21.09 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively were below those recommended by USEPA which stand at 120 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively (USEPA, 2005). Additionally, As(III) was less toxic than

the others and its CMC and CCC was, 169.2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 34 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ which was also lower than USEPA standard of 340 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 150 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively (USEPA, 2009). The aquatic life criteria derived in this study were closed to the value report by previous researchers (Shauhaimi-Othman *et al.*, 2012a; b, Wu *et al.*, 2012; Zheng *et al.*, 2017, Li *et al.*, 2021). Although, the ACR value of 9.9 in this study was also greater than the ACR values used by previous researchers.

A comparison of toxicity of metals to freshwater organisms showed that among the five metals studied, Cd was extremely toxic to the organisms (followed by Pb, Cr(IV), Zn and As(III). Additionally, based on other international standards (Table 3.2), all the standards (USEPA, CCME and UNECE) classification states that Cd exhibited greater toxicity than Pb to freshwater organisms.

Table 2
FAV, CMC and CCC value for Pb, Cr(IV), Cd, As(III) and Zn

	Pb ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Cr(VI) ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Cd ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	As(III) ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Zn ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
FAV	16.6	97	2.86	336.6	208.8
CMC = 1/2FAV	8.3	48.5	1.43	169.2	104.4
CCC=FAV/ACR^a	1.68	9.79	0.29	34.0	21.09
USEPA (CMC)	65.0	16	2	340	120
CCC	2.5	11	0.25	150	120
CCME	1	1	0.008	5	30
UNECE (Class 1)	<0.1	<1	0.007	3-10	<45

^aACR = 9.9 (From May *et al.*, 2016), USEPA (2005); CCME (1999); UNECE (1994)

Similarly, various studies also indicated that Cd has greater toxicity than Pb to freshwater organisms, for instance the fish *Danio Rerio* (Mu *et al.*, 2014), *Cyprinus Carpio* (Ciu *et al.*, 2021), *Chironomus Plumosus* (Vedamanikan & Shazili 2008)

and *Acipenser Transmontanus* (Vardy *et al.*, 2014). According to Luoma & Rainbow (2008), the relative toxicity of metals can differ among different organisms, influenced by factors that affect metal uptake rates. When metals

accumulate in undesired locations within organisms, they can disrupt important molecular functions, leading to toxicity. Toxic effects occur when the availability of metals surpasses a certain threshold, demonstrating that the degree of uptake surpasses both secretion and detoxification processes. Furthermore, Khangarot, (1991) stated that the toxicity of heavy metal ions is ascribed to their ability to bind with enzyme ligands essential for biological processes. Although enzyme inhibition may not be the main factor in determining the toxicity of non-transitional metal cations, other colligative factors such as osmotic pressure can lead to physical damage within cellular systems.

The CMC and CCC values for Pd, Cr(VI), Cd, As(III), and Zn determined in our research offer essential data for establishing national and local Water Quality Criteria (WQC) for metals. A numerical WQC represents the maximum concentration of a particular substance that would not induce significant adverse effects, either acutely or chronically, on aquatic organisms or their ecological functions. Aquatic ecosystems have a certain level of resilience and can withstand some amount of stress and negative impacts. Hence, it is most imperative to safeguard all species in every instance and location. Consequently, the goal of setting numerical national aquatic life criteria is

not to maintain uniform concentrations continuously to support the survival and procreation of all species within a given ecosystem. Instead, its purpose is to ensure sufficient protection for ecologically significant organisms as well as commercially valuable species in aquatic environments most of the time, while avoiding over-protection or inadequate protection (USEPA 1985).

Ecological risk assessment

The recurrent uncovering of the escalating concentrations of heavy metal in freshwater environments emphasizes the necessity of evaluating potential ecological impact. Fig. 2 shows the concentrations of exposure at the surface of heavy metals reported in Ntawogba creek, with detailed information listed in Table S2. The level of heavy metals in surface waters were 0.66 ± 0.18 mg/L, 1.84 ± 0.58 mg/L, 0.05 ± 0.02 mg/L and 30.95 ± 5.08 mg/L for Pb, Cr, Cd, As and Zn respectively. The Zinc showed the highest exposure concentration followed by chromium, cadmium, lead and arsenic. The results showed that the levels of heavy metals in Ntawogba Creek were greater than those recorded in other rivers worldwide, as indicated in Table S3. This may be related to the high level of anthropogenic activities taking place along the river course (Iyama *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 2
Concentration of Heavy Metals in surface water of Ntawogba Creek

Potential Ecological Risk of Heavy Metals

The severe toxicity of heavy metals to aquatic organisms has garnered a lot of public interest to the ecological risks they pose to aquatic environments. The HQ values (Fig. 3) were obtained by normalizing the heavy metals concentration of waters with CCC as reported by Wang *et al.*, (2020) which employed the hazard quotient (HQ) method. The comparison between the

heavy metal concentrations in surface waters and the CCC revealed that the highest mean HQ in Ntawogba Creek (HQ, 6.33). Cadmium (Cd) has a distinct impact on aquatic life, with aquatic organisms exhibiting significantly greater sensitivity to Cd exposure compared to humans. (Wright & Welbourn, 2002). Cd has been found to present a greater ecological risk to freshwater habitat compared to other heavy metals (Garai *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 3
Box Plot of HQ value of Ecological Risk in Surface Water

The calculated HQ values of Pb, and Cr were below 1 in all site, whereas Cd, As and Zn were above 1. Figure 3 shows HQ values of Pb, Cr, Cd, As, and Zn on aquatic biota. As indicated in figure 3 Cd, As, and Zn pose high ecological risk to sensitive aquatic organism (Plants, Crustaceans and Fishes) as compared to Pb and Cr which pose no ecological risk. The HQ calculated in this study indicated that the ecological risk of heavy metal to aquatic organism in Ntawogba surface water should be thoroughly examined, particularly with regard to its long-term effect of heavy metal exposure to aquatic organism.

Conclusion

This study revealed that cadmium exhibited the highest toxicity among the five metals tested on freshwater organisms, followed by lead, chromium

(IV), arsenic (III), and zinc. The CMC and CCC values for Pb, Cr(IV), Cd, As(III) and Zn determined from this study are 8.5, 48.5, 1.43, 169.2 and 104.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and 1.68, 9.79, 0.29, 34.0 and 34.0 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. According to the derived criteria, the assessment of ecological risk was conducted according to the Hazzard Quotient (HQ) method and the result shows that Pb and Cr posed no ecological risk, while Cd, As and Zn posed significant ecological risk to aquatic life, exposing an extensive number of species at risk in Ntawogba Creek. In order to protect aquatic life in Nigeria, water quality standards based on ALC must be established in addition to the country's drinking water standards. The present study contributes to a better understanding of the environmental risks of metals in

Nigeria and offers a scientific foundation for the conservation of aquatic species and aquatic ecosystem management in the nation, even though the results are still subject to experimentation and future applications.

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